

ORGANIZATIONAL ECONOMIC FOUNDATIONS OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF AGROCLUSTERS

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<p>Received: 14-10-2022 Accepted: 17-10-2022 Published: 22-10-2022</p>	<p>Abstract: Ushbu maqolada mamlakatimizda iqtisodiy islohotlarni amalga oshirish jarayonida innovatsiyalar va raqamli texnologiyalarga asoslangan yangicha xo'jalik yuritish sharoitlarida ishlash qobiliyatiga ega mutaxassislarni tayyorlash eng asosiy vazifa bo'lib qolmoqda. Bugungi bozor iqtisodiyoti sharoitida iqtisodiyotdagi nazariy va amaliy masalalarni hal etish zaruriyati tashkiliy iqtisodiy asoslari ochib berilgan.</p> <p>Keywords: bozor iqtisodiyoti, islohot, innovatsiya, texnologiya, ishlab chiqarish, raqamli, fermer xo'jaliklar, qishloq xo'jaligi, klaster, investitsiya, manfaat, integratsiya.</p> <p>About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.</p>
<p>Received: 14-10-2022 Accepted: 17-10-2022 Published: 22-10-2022</p>	<p>Abstract: In this article, in the process of implementing economic reforms in our country, the main task is to train specialists with the ability to work in new economic conditions based on innovations and digital technologies. Under the conditions of today's market economy, the need to solve theoretical and practical issues in the economy, the organizational economic foundations have been revealed.</p> <p>Keywords: market economy, reform, innovation, technology, production, digital, farms, agriculture, cluster, investment, interest, integration.</p> <p>About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.</p>
<p>Received: 14-10-2022 Accepted: 17-10-2022 Published: 22-10-2022</p>	<p>Abstract: В данной статье в процессе реализации экономических реформ в нашей стране основной задачей является подготовка специалистов, способных работать в новых экономических условиях на основе инноваций и цифровых технологий. В условиях современной рыночной экономики выявлена необходимость решения теоретических и практических вопросов в экономике, организационно-экономических основ.</p> <p>Keywords: рыночная экономика, реформа, инновации, технологии, производство, цифровые, фермы, сельское хозяйство, кластер, инвестиции, интерес, интеграция.</p> <p>About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.</p>

Introduction. In the process of implementing economic reforms in our country, training specialists with the ability to work in new economic conditions based on innovations and digital technologies remains the most important task. In the conditions of today's market economy, the need to solve theoretical and practical issues in the economy is directly related to the training of specialists with a high level of knowledge and skills based on the improvement of educational processes in the higher education system. Perfect organization of all types of

production and scientific practices in the educational system is of particular importance in the implementation of these goals.

The years of independence are spent with the implementation of large-scale reforms aimed at defining the perspective of the socio-economic and cultural development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, striving to take a worthy place among the countries of the world community. Studying the experiences of the developed countries of the world, taking into account local conditions, economic and intellectual resources, the implementation of fundamental reforms in all spheres of society ensures new achievements.

The farms operating in our republic are not only engaged in the production of agricultural goods, but also primarily preserve, process, and package the agricultural and livestock products grown by them and deliver them to consumers in a ready manner, as well as market demand. and it should be emphasized that, based on the proposal, they provide various services in rural areas and increase the financial stability of the economy.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 17, 2019 No. PF-5708 "On measures to improve the state management system in the field of agriculture" was adopted. In this Decree, one of the important tasks is to "implement measures for the widespread introduction of the cluster model of agribusiness, improve the organizational, legal and economic foundations of the clustering process, and support the implementation of investment projects on the organization and development of clusters in agricultural sectors" marked.¹²

Research methodology: This indicates the urgency of finding scientific-methodical solutions to normative-legal, organizational-technological, financial-economic and other issues related to the formation of clusters. In the implementation of this strategic task, proposals and recommendations developed based on the results of the conference "Development of the cluster system in agriculture: experiences, results and promising directions" are important.

This is reflected in the mutual relations between the enterprises included in the cluster, in the harmony of cooperation and competition, and in their operation based on public and private sector partnerships.

Analysis and Results. The following conditions are necessary for the formation of a cluster as a successful and effective structure¹³:

1. Initiative - entrepreneurs, representatives of authorities, public organizations, educational institutions, people with initiative and authority, with their reputation, intelligence, organizational skills and knowledge, are interested in

¹² Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 17, 2019 PF-5708 "On measures to improve the state management system in the field of agriculture"

¹³ Войнаренко М.П. Кластерные модели объединения предприятий в Украине // Экономическое возрождение России / М.П. Войнаренко. - 2007. - №4.

the benefits of clusters for their members and the region, and to prove

2. Innovation - new technologies in the organization of production, sales, management, financing provide new opportunities in the fight against competition.

3. Information - freedom, transparency, exchange of knowledge, the creation of databases and web pages open the way to markets for the supply of products, skilled labor, and labor tools.

4. Integration - provides for the application of new technologies of cooperation at the branch and regional level of enterprises, through the support of science and authorities.

5. Interest - entrepreneurship or public structure provides the basic condition of life activity, that is, it provides for the existence of interest of cluster participants and their achievement of economic benefit

The term "cluster", when translated from the English word "cluster", is a combination, collection of a number of similar elements, in the sense of a group and as an independent unit with certain characteristics. used in mathematics and, mostly, natural sciences. In the 1970s, Swedish economists K.Fredriksson and L.Lindmarks in the economy¹⁴ used the term cluster to define the concentration of enterprises in a limited area.

The advantage of the cluster form of business is that the use of the cluster method is of great importance, especially for the regions where the enterprises are related to each other. Clusters play a major role in strengthening the economic independence of regions. This approach makes it possible to identify economically priority industries and projects.

Annual production volume of "Nanyang red cotton angel textile" limited liability company in Izboskan district

Table 1

No	Indicators	Unit of measure	2020	2021	Ratio %
1	Annual production capacity	tons	4350	5800	133
2	Number of workers	person	270	296	110
3	The main raw material required (cotton fiber)	tons	5000	6000	120
4	Quantity of product produced	tons	4820	5536	115
5	Manufactured product	million	70854	90790	112
6	The price of the manufactured product in	a thousand	14,7	16,4	112

¹⁴ Spatial analysis, industry and the industrial environment. Progress in research and applications. Vol. 1. Industrial systems / Edited by F.E.I. Hamilton and Linge G.J. R.Chichester, N. Y. Brisbane, Toronto: Wiley, 1979.

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Table 1 shows the annual production volume of "Nanyang red cotton angel textile" limited liability company in Izboskan district. The table shows that in 2020-2021, the annual production volume of "Nanyang red cotton angel textile" limited liability company in Izboskan district production volume is increasing.

Conclusion and Recommendations. In short, to improve the continuous and efficient method of cotton production, storage, and processing in agroclusters, which is considered a new innovative system, to provide the domestic consumer market with cotton products, and to ensure food security by further increasing the export potential, in this regard It is necessary to consistently strengthen the scientific and research work, to pay special attention to solving the urgent problems of increasing the economic efficiency of cotton cultivation based on the use of water-saving technology.

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